

Using Generative Artificial Intelligence to Support Learning at Different Levels of Bloom's Taxonomy of Cognitive Goals - With a Specific Focus on Language and Literature Education

1. Generative Artificial Intelligence, A Phenomenon of Today

Generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) is a type of artificial intelligence (Bandi et al., 2023; IBM, n.d.) that can create new content (text, graphics, music), analyse it and also communicate with users through “natural human language”. Thanks to this, anyone can use it, the GenAI tools are intuitive and easy to use, and a large part of these tools are available free of charge. Generative AI tools are trained on a large amount of human-generated data, so they also have a large (not unlimited) knowledge base - in practice, this means that they can answer a wide range of questions, but their answers are not always error-free, and errors (called hallucinations) can occur. GenAI can do much more, however - it can explain and adapt to the age of the user, for example, and it can be personalised and adapted to specific needs or gamified.

Among the most popular generative AI tools are those that use so-called large language models (LLM) (European Commission, 2023; Microsoft, 2023) - specifically ChatGPT, Gemini, Copilot and others. These are specifically trained on human-generated textual materials (databases, websites, articles, books, etc.), but more recently also on materials created by the AI itself. The models are constantly being improved, capable of, for example, advanced reasoning, in-depth research, etc.

1.1 *Opportunities and Risks of Using GenAI in School*

In primary and secondary schools, generative AI can be used to create personalised learning materials and interactive tasks that can be tailored to the age and individual needs of students. With the ability to analyse data on individual student performance, AI can make it easier for teachers to adapt the content and pace of instruction. Teachers can use these tools to prepare teaching materials, create tests and automate routine tasks, saving time that can then be used for things like guided discussions and individual student support.

Another benefit of AI in schools is the automation of feedback and assessment of student work, allowing teachers to spend more time interacting directly with children. This is because tools based on generative AI can quickly analyse and correct assignments, helping to identify weaknesses in pupils' knowledge and then design exercises tailored to their needs based on these. This increases the effectiveness of teaching or reduces the administrative burden on teachers. However, AI should only be considered as a support tool; the content it generates must be controlled or corrected by teachers (Galindo-Domínguez et al., 2024).

Other advantages of AI include the ability to interact autonomously with the pupil, for example, it can automatically invent tasks for pupils to complete, AI evaluates them and further motivates pupils. In case of failure, it can then guide them to the correct solution. The range of applications of generative AI is very wide indeed. On the other hand, the assignments need to be thought out so that it is truly functional and support, not replace, student activity (Kopecký Kamil, 2024).

In secondary schools, the use of generative AI is expanding to support more complex tasks and projects. Students can use it to write reports, create more complex texts or even generate visual content, allowing them to better understand and apply theoretical knowledge in practice. Such an approach also helps to develop creative thinking, as students are encouraged to experiment with new ideas and concepts, as AI can provide students with such ideas and thus inspire them. Research shows that the use of generative tools, for example in homework, contributes to greater student engagement and more effective learning (Kopecký Kamil et al., 2024).

However, integrating generative AI into education requires not only the establishment of ethical standards, but also thoughtful pedagogical practices. When planning tasks and assignments, teachers should take into account that students may use AI - thus it is important to formulate assignments in such a way that the use of these tools either supports the learning objectives or clearly defines when and how their use is permissible. While these technologies can greatly enhance the effectiveness and personalisation of learning, it is essential that they are not seen as a replacement for the human teacher, but rather as a support for them. Thus, educators must be prepared to correctly interpret and use AI outputs while teaching students how to critically evaluate information. The results of studies (Chen & Hou, 2024; Jauhainen & Guerra, 2023; Villan & P. dos Santos, 2023) confirm that appropriately used AI can significantly contribute to the quality of the educational process while helping to reduce teachers' workload.

A Research conducted in the Czech environment (Kopecký et al., 2024) show that generative AI tools are actually used by approximately half of Czech pupils (43.67% of primary school pupils and 67.5% of secondary school pupils, especially ChatGPT - 53.99%). Various AI tools are used by pupils in both positive and ethical ways (e.g. for inspiration or self-study) and unethical ways - e.g. to generate entire homework assignments (28.04%), to solve examples and equations (20.78%) and to cheat on tests (6.33%). At the same time, however, pupils reported that only in a quarter of cases AI is regularly used in their school.

The STEM agency conducted a survey of 11-19 year olds. Data was collected through an online questionnaire. The aim of the research was to find out about Generation Z's learning habits, preferences and use of AI tools in education. The research suggests that only 25% of students frequently use various online resources and materials for learning. A total of 45% of students have used AI tools, with ChatGPT being the most popular with 89%. AI tools are mainly used in teaching in the subjects of English language, foreign language and mathematics. A total of

34% of students reported that teachers discouraged or prohibited them from using AI tools. Only 24% of respondents had solved tasks that required the use of AI tools (STEM, 2024).

A more recent survey was conducted by the IPSOS company with over 800 Czech pupils aged 12 to 17. The research shows that a total of 87% of respondents use AI. Three quarters of respondents consider it important that their teachers are proficient in GenAI tools and are able to connect teaching with the possibilities that AI presents. Also interesting is the finding that more than half of respondents believe that grading with AI can be more fair. This view is more likely to be held by pupils whose school has anchored the use of AI tools in its standards (IPSOS, 2025).

The phenomenon of generative artificial intelligence affects not only primary and secondary school teachers, but also academics and university lecturers. The authors of *The manifesto for teaching and learning in a time of Generative AI: A critical collective stance to better navigate the future* (Bozkurt et al., 2024) point to the advent of these technologies as a major turning point in the understanding of education. The manifesto was developed as a result of collective writing and expert consensus using the Delphi method, reflecting a wide range of views from different cultural and academic backgrounds.

Although GenAI promises personalized learning, greater efficiency and accessibility of education, the authors stress that these tools are not ideologically or culturally neutral. Algorithms shape interactions, communication, and content creation, raising fundamental questions about how GenAI affects people's ability to act on their own initiative.

The main conclusions of the Manifesto can be summarised as follows:

- **GenAI integration requires a critical approach** - the role of the human being and the need to maintain human judgement is key.
- **GenAI is not ideologically neutral** - it reflects cultural values and can reinforce stereotypes and marginalise certain groups.
- **Risks to creativity and critical thinking** - over-reliance on AI can undermine deeper cognitive processes and lead to superficial learning.
- **Ethical considerations and responsibility** - a society-wide debate on the ethical use of GenAI is necessary, especially with respect to algorithmic biases, copyright and privacy.
- **GenAI may intensify the digital abyss** - the disparity in unequal access to technology and competencies may widen.
- **Importance of AI literacy education** - students and educators should be guided to understand how GenAI works, its limitations and opportunities.

The authors also openly acknowledge the limitations of the study. It is a speculative document based on collective thinking, not empirical research. Consensus among all participants was difficult to achieve, and often the positive and negative aspects are in tension or contradictory. In conclusion, the Manifesto calls for a collective, informed and ethically anchored approach to integrating GenAI into education - not as a ready-made solution, but as a challenge that forces us to redefine the values, goals and shape of education in the 21st century.

2 GenAI in Education in the Context of Bloom's Taxonomy

Bloom's Taxonomy of Cognitive Objectives is a tool used to plan and evaluate instructional objectives in education, categorized by level of difficulty of thought operations. The taxonomy was originally created by American psychologist Benjamin Bloom in 1956 and was revised in 2001 (Anderson & Krathwohl, 2001; Stanny, 2016; Wilson, 2016). The taxonomy consists of six main levels (expressed by verbs): remember, understand, apply, analyze, evaluate, and create. These levels represent different cognitive goals that go from the simplest memorization of information to complex evaluation and creation of new ideas. In addition, the revised taxonomy is supplemented with knowledge dimensions - factual knowledge (what students need to know about the discipline), conceptual knowledge (i.e., relationships between elements of more complex structures), procedural knowledge (i.e., how to do something - methods, criteria, skills), and metacognitive knowledge (i.e., general knowledge, reasoning about one's own thinking, etc.).

In practice, we can simplistically imagine that some of the tasks we give pupils only require memorising information - for example, naming word classes in Czech. However, other tasks require not only memory but also the ability to apply the knowledge gained, such as solving a word problem in mathematics. In this case, thinking is involved in addition to memory. The aim is for pupils to gradually master increasingly challenging tasks and thus develop their skills.

Researchers at Oregon State University (Oregon State University, 2024) have updated Bloom's Taxonomy to account for the growing use of generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) in education. They added new perspectives to the traditional hierarchy of cognitive levels, which includes remembering, understanding, applying, analyzing, evaluating, and creating, reflecting AI capabilities and unique human skills. Their approach emphasizes a rethinking of learning objectives and assessment so that students not only use AI as a tool, but also develop deeper critical thinking, creativity, and decision-making skills. The result is a framework that helps educators adapt educational strategies to a reality in which AI can generate answers, analyze data, or synthesize information, while humans maintain a key role in interpretation, ethical reasoning, and innovation.

Bloom's Taxonomy Revisited

Use this table as a reference for evaluating and considering changes to aligned course activities (or, where possible, learning outcomes) that emphasize distinctive human skills and/or integrate generative AI (GenAI) tools as a supplement to the learning process.

All course activities and assessments will benefit from ongoing review given the evolving capabilities of GenAI tools.

Version 2.0 (2024)

This work is licensed under CC BY-NC 4.0

	Distinctive Human Skills	How GenAI Can Supplement Learning*
CREATE	Engage in both creative and cognitive processes that leverage human lived experiences, social-emotional interactions, intuition, reflection, and judgment to formulate original solutions	Support brainstorming processes; suggest a range of alternatives; enumerate potential drawbacks and advantages; describe successful real-world cases; create a tangible deliverable based on human inputs
EVALUATE	Engage in metacognitive reflection; holistically appraise ethical consequences of other courses of action; identify significance or situate within a full historical or disciplinary context	Identify pros and cons of various courses of action; develop and check against evaluation rubrics
ANALYZE	Critically think and reason within the cognitive and affective domains; justify analysis in depth and with clarity	Compare and contrast data, infer trends and themes in a narrowly-defined context; compute; predict; interpret and relate to real-world problems, decisions, and choices
APPLY	Operate, implement, conduct, execute, experiment, and test in the real world; apply human creativity and imagination to idea and solution development	Make use of a process, model, or method to solve a quantitative or qualitative inquiry; assist students in determining where they went wrong while solving a problem
UNDERSTAND	Contextualize answers within emotional, moral, or ethical considerations; select relevant information; explain significance	Accurately describe a concept in different words; recognize a related example; translate to another language
REMEMBER	Recall information in situations where technology is not readily accessible	Retrieve factual information; list possible answers; define a term; construct a basic chronology or timeline

*AI capabilities derived with reference to an analysis of the MAGE framework, based on ChatGPT 4 as of October 2023. See Zaphir, L., Lodge, J. M., Lisee, J., McGrath, D., & Khosravi, H. (2024). How critically can an AI think? A framework for evaluating the quality of thinking of generative artificial intelligence. arXiv preprint arXiv:2406.14769.

Figure 1 Revising Bloom's taxonomy using generative AI (Oregon State University, 2024)

3 The Use of Generative Artificial Intelligence at Different Levels of Bloom's Taxonomy of Cognitive Objectives

In order to be able to effectively use generative AI tools (especially in the form of LLM), it is necessary to be able to correctly formulate the tasks (so-called prompts) that we feed into these tools (Korzynski et al., 2023; Peck, 2023; Walter, 2024; Willey et al., 2023). The prompts should be as specific, precise, clear, and provide context as possible - this will reduce the chances of the AI producing unwanted outputs. It is then always necessary to check the result; even if the prompts are correctly entered, the AI may make a mistake.

In the following section, we will introduce the different types of prompts that target each level of Bloom's taxonomy in relation to the goals of those levels. Prompts are constructed from the perspective of the learner and are not personalized with respect to age or knowledge.

1. Remember

The first level of taxonomy - **remember** - aims to store and recall knowledge from long-term memory, such as concepts, definitions and basic facts. Associated with this level are active

verbs such as *know, recognize, recall, assign, sort, repeat, reproduce, name, define, describe, write or complete*. Specific information can be uploaded to a tool like ChatGPT from which assignments will then be generated - for example, lists of authors and works, state capitals, examples of specific words, chemical elements, and so on. This is one way to target the creation of assignments to specific, covered school material. In this way, the teacher can narrow down the number of examples the students will work with, and these examples can match exactly what the students should be practicing. Below is a table with examples of prompts.

Table 1

Examples of prompts for the remember level in Bloom's Taxonomy

Subject/Field of Study	Example of a Prompt
Czech Language	<i>Ask me different questions about cases in czech grammar and I will write down the case numbers. If you get it wrong, repeat the correct answer so I can remember it better.</i>
Literature	<i>Give me the names of literary works from the Middle Ages and I will match them with authors. If you get it wrong, repeat the correct answer so I can remember it better.</i>
Literature	<i>Give me the motifs of literary works from the Renaissance and the names of the main characters, and I'll match the work and author to them. Any assignments I got wrong, ask again.</i>
Chemistry	<i>Select a chemical element. I'll tell you its chemical symbol. Check if I answered correctly.</i>
History	<i>Give me key historical dates, like the beginning of World War I, and I will tell you what happened then. If I answer incorrectly, correct me.</i>
Biology	<i>Give me a list of the anatomical parts of the human body and I will match them to the correct area of the body. Check my answer for accuracy.</i>
Philosophy	<i>Name the major philosophical movements of the 19th century and I will identify which philosopher (or philosophers) belong to them. If I'm wrong, correct me.</i>
Geography	<i>Give me the names of a few ancient civilizations and I will tell you where in the world they were located. Check to see if I've answered correctly.</i>
English Language	<i>Give me the words in English and I will translate them into Czech.</i>

2. Understand

The second level of Bloom's taxonomy is **comprehension/understanding**, which aims to construct meaning from the information received, to convert it into another form or to explain it in one's own words. Typical active verbs associated with this level include *interpret, express in one's own words, express in another form, convert, summarize, calculate, estimate, explain, clarify, substantiate, or classify*.

Table 2

Examples of prompts for the remember level in Bloom's Taxonomy

Subject/Field of Study	Example of A Prompt
Native Language	<i>Make up sentences with words that can be replaced by synonyms. Mark these words in the sentence and I will come up with synonyms for them. Check the solution for me.</i>
Native Language	<i>Give me groups of synonyms, in which there will always be one word that is not synonymous with the others. If I make a mistake, explain the correct solution.</i>
Czech Language	<i>You give me sentences and I will fill try to choose appropriate adverbs.</i>
Biology	<i>Read me a short text about photosynthesis and ask me to rephrase it into a simpler form. Check that I have understood the key ideas correctly.</i>
Mathematics	<i>Give me a mathematical example with a fraction, for example $\frac{3}{4}$, and ask me to explain what it means. If the explanation is incorrect, correct me.</i>
Science	<i>Describe a process to me, such as the water cycle, and I will explain what happens in each stage. See if I understand correctly.</i>
History	<i>Read me a short story from Czech history, such as the Battle of White Mountain, and ask me to explain why this event was important. Check that I have understood the main ideas.</i>

3. Apply

The third level of Bloom's taxonomy is application, which aims to apply learned knowledge, skills or methods to solve problems in new situations. At this stage, learners are expected to be able to transfer theoretical knowledge into practice and actively use it. Typical active verbs include: *perform, use, apply, implement, demonstrate, design, prove, (re)solve, try*.

Table 3*Examples of prompts for the remember level in Bloom's Taxonomy*

Subject/Field of Study	Example of A Prompt
Mathematics	<i>Give me a math problem using the Pythagorean theorem, for example, calculate the length of a side of the right triangle. I will tell you how I would calculate it, and you evaluate the correctness.</i>
Physics	<i>Describe a physics problem, such as calculating the kinetic energy of a car, and ask me to use the appropriate formula. Then check my calculations.</i>
Physics	<i>Describe a situation in which I have to apply Newton's second law. I will try to explain how this law works in the situation.</i>
Czech Language	<i>Choose a noun for me to use in my sentences. Check that I am adding the correct forms and writing them down correctly.</i>
Czech Language	<i>Pick me a feminine noun. I will make up sentences to go with it. Check that I'm using the correct forms and spelling them correctly.</i>

4. Analyze

The fourth level of Bloom's taxonomy focuses on analysis, which aims to break down the material into parts, identify the relationships between these parts, and understand their interrelationships. At this stage, students learn to critically examine information, identify structure, recognize arguments, and distinguish between facts and opinions. Active verbs characteristic of this level include: *analyze, analyze, distinguish, organize, attribute, decide*.

Table 4*Examples of prompts for the remember level in Bloom's Taxonomy*

Subject/Field of Study	Example of A Prompt
History	<i>Present me with a text about the Industrial Revolution and ask me to identify the main causes and consequences of each event. Evaluate whether I have correctly distinguished between causes and effects.</i>
Czech Language	<i>Give me a group of words that belong to a Czech language phenomenon. I will try to find out what it is.</i>

Czech Language	<i>Give me a group of words that belong to a Czech language phenomenon. Always add one word that does not belong to the group. I will try to find out which one it is.</i>
Chemistry	<i>Describe the chemical reaction to me and I will try to break the process down into its various stages, including a description of what happens to the reactants and products.</i>
Mathematics	<i>Give me a complex math problem and I will break it down into steps. Check that I've got the order of the steps right.</i>
Science	<i>Describe a multi-step problem, such as an environmental problem, and ask me to break it down into causes, effects and solutions.</i>
History	<i>Give me a short text on the differences between democracy and dictatorship and ask me to compare the main features of these two political systems.</i>

5. Evaluate

The fifth level of Bloom's taxonomy is evaluation, which aims to assess the value of information, arguments, or methods based on predetermined criteria and standards. This level requires the ability to critically evaluate different approaches, assess their merits or shortcomings, and defend one's own judgement. Typical active verbs include: *check, assess, evaluate, state pros and cons, criticize, justify.*

Table 5

Examples of prompts for the remember level in Bloom's Taxonomy

Subject/Field of study	Example of A Prompt
History	<i>Describe a historical event to me and I will judge whether the actions taken at the time were right or wrong given the conditions at the time.</i>
Citizenship Education	<i>Present me with a story about a relationship between two friends where one does something wrong, and ask me to judge whether his behaviour was right or wrong and what I would have done differently in that situation.</i>
Chemistry	<i>Present me with a scientific experiment and ask me to judge whether the correct methods were used. If I find any errors, ask me to suggest improvements.</i>
Native Language	<i>Provide me with arguments as to why a particular technology (such as mobile phones) should be banned and ask me to judge whether the reasons given are justified or exaggerated.</i>

Native Language *Give me a controversial opinion, for example 'electric cars are green', and ask me to argue for and against that statement. Then evaluate my arguments.*

6 Create

The sixth and highest level of Bloom's taxonomy is creation, which aims to create new and original wholes from different elements or information, which involves creativity and innovation. Students at this level combine existing knowledge to design a new solution, concept or product. Typical active verbs are: *create, construct, design, draw general conclusions, reorganize, classify.*

Table 6

Examples of prompts for the remember level in Bloom's Taxonomy

Subject/Field of Study	Example of A Prompt
Geography	<i>Give me some key information about climate change and ask me to propose a plan to improve the environment. Evaluate whether my proposal covers all important aspects.</i>
Czech Language	<i>Present me with various story elements (e.g. characters, setting, conflict) and ask me to create an original story from them. Evaluate how well I was able to connect all the elements into a coherent plot.</i>
Citizenship Education	<i>Give me a hypothetical situation, for example "the city is dealing with homelessness", and ask me to propose a solution. Indicate what steps I should take, who I would involve in the solution, and what impact my proposal might have. Judge my proposal.</i>
Czech Language	<i>Ask me to create a new story based on a classic fairy tale but change the setting and some of the characters to set the story in modern times. Evaluate how well I was able to adapt the original idea to the new setting.</i>
Czech Language	<i>Create a model event such as "accident on the D1 highway" or "egg shortage in US stores" and just give me keywords and basic information. Ask me to create a news story about the event. Evaluate how well I was able to produce the given text in relation to similar texts of the same type. Try to suggest improvements.</i>

4 Support for Mother Tongue Education

One of the areas where generative AI tools can be used, is native language teaching. In this section, we focus on several activities that can be implemented using a common LLM (ChatGPT, Gemini, Copilot, Grok, etc.). The activities can be adapted to the specific age of the

learners and their knowledge/skills (the prompts can be modified, for example, in the following way: create an activity for learners aged 13). The field of mother tongue normally comprises three components: communication and style education, language education and literary education ((*Rámcový Vzdělávací Program pro Základní Vzdělávání*, 2021)), and it is necessary not only to emphasise that the educational content of the individual components is intertwined in the teaching, but also that these three components cover the educational content of the non-specified mother tongue in a relatively comprehensive way, however the content is structured. On the basis of the created examples, it can be concluded that, for example, within the language issues, the vocabulary plane can be described as the most accessible for working with AI: in it, one can count on relatively isolated and well-defined units that can either be added to the proposed type of chain (e.g. Word Football) or interchanged according to the proposed formula (e.g. working with synonyms or antonyms). As the complexity of phenomena on the syntactic level increases, one can expect to see difficulties in formulating the task appropriately so that the result matches the expected output. The activities below are based on direct interaction with the AI and can be implemented both at school and, for example, in home training. The idea is, above all, to involve all pupils and to have the AI act as an assistant - not replacing the pupil's activities, but guiding them.

4.1 Activities for the Development of Linguistic and Metalinguistic Competence

4.1.1 Vocabulary Development

Vocabulary development can be trained with the help of didactic games, which language models can also help with. A typical example is the game **Word Football**. The principle of the game is very simple - the artificial intelligence offers us a word and our task is to create a new word from the last letter of the previous word. For example, how many syllables a word must have, which letters it must or must not contain, and so on. Word football with AI can be played across languages - both in text and spoken form - the AI can synthesise the human voice without any problems. According to Bloom's taxonomy, we are mainly at the level of apply (learners use words from their vocabulary), remember (they expand their vocabulary with new words) or analyze (they analyze the formal properties of words - for example, the first and last letter, the number of syllables, etc.).

The prompt for this game could be "*Play verbal football with me in Czech. I will start with the first word and you answer with the word that starts with the last letter of my word. We play on common nouns. If I get the answer wrong, give me a hint or explain why the answer is wrong. If I don't know, suggest three possibilities. Adjust the difficulty level according to how well I'm playing. If I repeat myself, give me a warning and offer a new word.*"

Another game can be, for example, **a search for synonyms or antonyms** - the AI offers the player a word and its goal is to find a synonym (a word of the same or similar meaning) or an antonym (a word of opposite meaning). The AI then evaluates whether the solution was correct and the game can continue. The task can also be made more difficult, for example, in the case of antonyms, by restricting the way the created words of opposite meaning should

look: use only the Czech prefix *-ne*, or some prefix of Latin origin (de, anti, re, etc.), or distinguish between word-formation and lexical way (safe - dangerous vs. big - small), etc. According to Bloom's taxonomy, students operate mainly at the levels of apply, remember and understand (they work with the substantive meaning of words).

The student can play this game by using the prompt: *"Play the Czech synonyms game with me. Give me a word and I will come up with a synonym for it. If I get the answer wrong, explain why and give me the correct answer. If I don't know, give me three options and help me understand them. Adjust the difficulty according to my level."*

4.1.2 Activities to Build Syntactic Competence

Artificial intelligence can be used **to train the formation of hypotactic sentences** in which various subordinate clauses are attached to the main clause. This is useful in situations where we need to express, for example, the local or temporal circumstances of an event, but also, for example, a cause, a condition, and so on. Here we aim according to Bloom's taxonomy at the level of apply or create. A prompt for this interactive activity might look like this, for example:

"You are an AI that helps students practice forming sentences with subordinate clauses. Students are given a simple sentence (main clause) and a type of subordinate clause to add. The pupil can modify the main clause (words or order) but the meaning must remain the same. Your task is to:

- 1. Come up with an initial main clause and choose an appropriate type of subordinate clause for the student to create.*
- 2. Check that the pupil has correctly created the desired type of subordinate clause.*
- 3. Assess whether the meaning of the main clause has been preserved.*
- 4. Provide immediate feedback as to whether the answer is correct.*
- 5. In case of error, explain everything and offer the correct solution.*
- 6. Encourage the pupil to continue practising.*
- 7. Repeat the procedure (i.e. create a new assignment)."*

The next activity may be slightly different. Although it has a similar focus to the previous activity, it requires more creativity and therefore corresponds more to the level of creation in Bloom's taxonomy:

"You are an AI that helps students practice forming sentences with subordinate clauses. The pupil is given a simple sentence in which one of the expressions is underlined (highlighted). The pupil should try to express the expression in a separate subordinate clause, and the subordinate clause should better show the meaning of the underlined expression in the simple sentence present in the assignment. Your task is to:

- 1. Make the initial sentence simple and choose an appropriate expression to be underlined so that it can be expressed in a separate subordinate clause.*
- 2. Check that the pupil has correctly formed a subordinate clause that independently develops the underlined expression present in the initial simple sentence.*

3. *Assess whether the meaning of the main clause has been preserved.*
4. *Provide immediate feedback as to whether the answer is correct.*
5. *In the event of an error, explain everything and offer the correct solution.*
6. *Encourage the pupil to continue practising.*
7. *Repeat the procedure (i.e. create a new assignment)."*

The prompt can be modified so that the student does not form but correctly determines the type of the subordinate clause. Thus, the artificial intelligence will prepare the initial language material and the learner will determine the type of sentences. From the point of view of Bloom's taxonomy, it is therefore primarily a level of analyze:

"You are an AI that helps students practice identifying the types of subordinate clauses in hypotactic sentences. You give students a finished sentence that contains one subordinate clause. His/her task is to correctly identify what type of subordinate clause it is (for example, subordinate clause subjunctive, object, attributive, predicative complement, or adverbial - place, time, manner, measure, cause, purpose, condition, concession).

Your job is:

1. *Invent a hypotactic sentence containing one subordinate clause.*
2. *Invite the student to identify the type of this subordinate clause.*
3. *Check that the student has correctly identified the type of the subordinate clause.*
4. *Provide immediate feedback on whether the answer is correct.*
5. *If there is an error, explain everything and give the correct solution.*
6. *Encourage the pupil to continue practising.*
7. *Repeat the procedure (i.e. create a new assignment)."*

4.1.3 Development of Spelling Competence

Using AI, it is relatively easy to create **interactive exercises focused on Czech spelling**. However, it is necessary to take into account that AI can make mistakes (although it is constantly improving and the number of errors is decreasing) - LLMs are not primarily trained on Czech spelling and can make mistakes in some situations (rather grammatical than spelling). However, this can be eliminated by training the AI (adding new knowledge to it), or by creating the exercises ourselves.

Interaction in this context means that the AI will provide feedback to the student and motivate them to further activities. A simple spelling test can be created using this prompt: *"I am a teacher and I want the AI to practice the listed words after B interactively with the student. The AI should enter one word with a space (for example, b_dlet) in a short sentence, ask the student to complete the correct form and immediately after their answer provide feedback - praise, or correct and explain the rule. Then continue with the next word, a total of 10 words."*

An interesting possibility offered by generative artificial intelligence tools is **the generation, and especially the reading, of dictations "on demand"**. That is, artificial intelligence can

create a dictation (or any other spelling exercise) focused on specific spelling phenomena and read it to the student... and then let the student correct the dictation and display the correct solution.

4.2 Activities for Developing Stylistic, Communication and Creative Writing Skills

The following activities, which serve to develop communication competences, reach the level of create in terms of Bloom's taxonomy, but depending on the specific topic, they also move to all lower levels. The assignment in this area can be quite specific and can be based on the traditional model of stylistic units with a focus on production according to a pattern/text model. However, it can also have a more complex character and develop communication competence more (1) in the area of traditional stylistic techniques (e.g. narration, argumentation, etc.) or (2) in broader contexts linked to everyday life situations (e.g. lunch in a restaurant, a visit to the doctor, shopping), for which the terms *schema*, *scenario*, *framework*, *script* ((Müllerová et al., 1992) are used in cognitive linguistics or cognitively oriented pragmatics (D'hondt et al., 2009).

An example could be an activity involving a (simple) description – students create a description of a specific object (a room, something in their surroundings) and then formulate a prompt, using which they have an image of the given object generated (for example, in Microsoft Copilot) and compare whether the result corresponds to their assignment and reality. They then try to modify the prompt so that the AI output is as accurate as possible. A sample prompt could then look like this: „*Create an image of a table and a chair, on the table is a mug of coffee and a flower. The table is by the window, the sun is shining through the window*”.

Advanced versions of artificial intelligence can analyze real-world images from a phone, so it is possible, for example, to create a description of a specific room and compare it with the output of the artificial intelligence. It is also possible to ask the artificial intelligence (similar to a teacher) to suggest a logical structure for the description: „*I need advice on how to proceed when I want to describe a room. Can you advise me on how to proceed (suggest a structure/outline)?*”

A similar approach can be used for other stylistic procedures and units, for example, when a student does not know how to internally structure his unit in a way that preserves the cohesion and coherence of the text, he can ask the AI for support. Examples of prompts might look like this: „*I am writing a motivation letter that I am attaching to an application for a teaching position. How should I proceed? How should the letter be structured?*” Or for example: “*I am writing an essay on global climate change. Can you advise me on what topics I should focus on?*”

4.2.1 Development of Communication Skills (Vocabulary, Sentence Formation, Stories, Creativity)

One way to develop children's communication skills is the interactive game "**Chain of Stories**", controlled by artificial intelligence. Players, including AI, take turns adding sentences to the story, thereby actively practicing vocabulary, grammar, style and creating a coherent text. The game develops the ability to express oneself coherently, logically organize thoughts and creativity.

Artificial intelligence can act as a teammate, corrector or facilitator – providing feedback, suggesting alternative formulations or setting language challenges. Thanks to its adaptability, it is possible to adapt the game to the age and level of the students, for example by choosing a genre or specific language elements. The game supports not only writing, but also text comprehension and critical perception of language, and can be used individually or in a group. The prompt for this game could be: *„Let’s play a game called Story Chain to help me develop my language skills. Start the story with one sentence and I’ll continue. Then we’ll take turns and work together to create a coherent story. If my sentence is unclear, ungrammatical, or disjointed, correct it and explain why. Also, occasionally suggest new words or phrases I could use and give me feedback on my sentence structure. If you want, you can add challenges along the way, such as ‘Use the word mysterious in the next sentence’ or ‘Use a simile.’ Adjust the difficulty to my level and help me improve. Start with the first sentence!”*

Another option is to start from a real existing text and complete it, where the student first becomes familiar with the story, which he will then complete. Familiarization with the text and interaction with artificial intelligence can of course take place both in text and auditory (sound). The benefit is that students simultaneously learn to speak coherently and express their thoughts.

Furthermore, it is possible to simulate a real communication situation with the help of AI in which the student has to interact with someone else (a salesperson, an official, a teacher...), and this can be both a written interaction (for example, a request for something in writing, a reaction to an answer, etc.) and a spoken communication (for example, a common situation when shopping). The activity itself can look like this - artificial intelligence prepares a random situation, chooses its role, the goal of communication and starts "playing". The student then communicates with AI and tries to achieve the communication goal, AI guides, evaluates, motivates it. The prompt can be as extensive as desired, in the following example we present one of the longer versions.

"You are an AI simulating a real communication situation for a student. Your task is to create a scenario in which the student will have to interact with you as with a specific person (for example, a salesperson, an official, a teacher, etc.) in a real-life situation using spoken communication. Communicate like a living person, react naturally, ask questions, create obstacles or complicate the situation according to your role. At the end of the communication, give the student brief feedback on his communication skills.

Follow the below structure:

1. *Describe the situation: Briefly and clearly explain to the student what is happening, where they are, and what their goal is (what they want to get or accomplish).*
2. *Explain your role: State who you are (e.g., a sales person in a store, an office worker, a teacher at school) and how you will behave (e.g., helpful, dismissive, neutral).*
3. *Invoke interaction: Invite the student to start talking to you and achieve the set goal (e.g., buy goods, fulfill a request, apologize for being late).*
4. *Interact naturally: Respond to the student's sentences, ask follow-up questions, or provide obstacles according to your role to make the communication realistic.*
5. *Conclusion and feedback: When the student achieves the goal or ends the communication, evaluate how well they did and give them specific feedback on their communication skills (e.g., politeness, clarity of expression, ability to respond to unexpected questions, etc.).*

Part of the development of stylistic and communication competences can also be **the creation of any prompts by the students themselves**. The students are given the task of creating a prompt for a specific teaching topic. They come up with and formulate the form of the task assignment (i.e. in what form they will receive the assigned material) and what the AI should assess during the check. The teaching topic is, for example, a specific spelling phenomenon that the students should practice (for example, the spelling of i/y after ambivalent consonants in the stems of words). The students can suggest that the exercise could be supplementary, and during the check the AI should explain the correct solutions. The teacher can use problem questions to guide students in what information is important to add to the assignment, for example, if the exercise is too long (*"What if the exercise is too long?"*), students may come to the realization that they could add information about the scope to the prompt. Or, for example, the teacher can ask what to do if the exercise is too difficult - students can then suggest adding information about the level (for example, easy, medium, difficult). The activity teaches students to express themselves accurately and is also important for students to be able to use AI functionally themselves.

The use of AI **for explanation** is very useful. Students can often find themselves in a situation where a certain topic is not clear enough for them, they miss some connection or relationship, and therefore they do not understand the curriculum. AI can describe the topic again, explain it, add other suitable examples that make the issue more concrete, etc. They must analyze what they see as the problem and reformulate it in the form of a prompt. Students can have AI describe how they understand the topic and verify whether they are thinking correctly, or guide them. By creating these prompts, students also develop their communication skills.

4.3 Support for Education in the Field of Literary and Media Education

Supporting education using GenAI in the field of literature education involves a multifaceted approach that integrates cognitive, emotional, and cultural dimensions to promote critical thinking, empathy, and cultural awareness among students. Hartman (2025) emphasizes that

GenAI can help students develop their literary literacy, for example, by mediating different texts. He further emphasizes that the use of GenAI can improve literature education by personalizing learning experiences and increasing engagement through tailored recommendations.

Artificial intelligence can be used for **reading comprehension training**. For example, it will create a sample text and tasks for the teacher, let the students read it and then ask them questions, which the students will answer. Everything will be immediately evaluated by the students. The prompt can be the following from the teacher's (student's) point of view: *„Create a short educational text in Czech suitable for 7th grade elementary school students. The text should be on the topic 'Life of bees in a hive' and should contain basic information that is understandable for children of this age. The text should be approximately 150 words long. Then ask me these questions directly as an artificial intelligence that interacts with them. Ask the questions in sequence - wait for my answer, evaluate it, ask the next question. There will be 8 questions in total and they will be focused on checking reading comprehension. The questions should be of different types - for example, a question to choose the correct answer from 4, etc., true/false, an open question requiring a short answer, and a question to assign the correct statement to a certain paragraph of the text, etc. After each answer, provide the student with immediate feedback on whether he answered correctly, and if necessary, correct the error and explain everything. Motivate, activate. At the end, summarize and evaluate everything.“*

Of course, it is possible to use a text prepared by the teacher, for which the AI will come up with questions and suitable tasks oriented towards the development of language competence. For example, you can work with common informative texts, popular educational texts, but also artistic texts.

AI tools can also generate **different types of literary texts according to the assignment**. The generated texts can serve as inspiration for discussion, analysis and some input into a certain topic. GenAI can help students with the interpretation of certain texts. The student can write his analysis of a literary work and the AI will offer recommendations based on algorithms to improve the interpretation. Based on the preferences entered by the student, the AI can recommend adequate works that can meet the student's wishes.

An interesting activity that can increase children's interest in poetry, for example, is **setting poems to music according to the students' specific preferences**. That is, students do not recite the poetry, or the teacher does not recite it, but they set it to music using AI (for example, the Suno tool), which allows them to choose different musical styles and genres. The result is attractive to students - it activates their attention and motivates them.

Furthermore, AI can be used to strengthen students' media literacy and develop their critical thinking. This can be done by using both authentic texts (which are spread on the Internet, for example), and photographs or videos. Both contemporary language material and period texts (propaganda, but also election materials - posters, etc.) can be used. Generative artificial intelligence tools can be used to train students in recognizing argumentative fouls or manipulative techniques. For example, a student can generate a manipulative text

themselves and ask the artificial intelligence tool to guide them in recognizing them. The prompt may look like this: *„Generate a short text for me that contains manipulation techniques and argumentative fouts, but don't mark them. I will analyze the text paragraph by paragraph. When I tell you which parts of the first paragraph I consider manipulative, tell me if I am right. If so, ask me why I marked that part. Then evaluate my answer and give me feedback on whether I explained it correctly. If I missed something, help me uncover it. When we finish the first paragraph, let's continue in the same way with the next one. Do this in a way that will help me gradually master the recognition of manipulation and argumentative fouts.“*

5 Limits and Restrictions on the Use of Generative Artificial Intelligence in Education

Although generative artificial intelligence offers many benefits in education, its use must be understood in the context of certain limitations – whether technical, age-related, linguistic or pedagogical. The first of these is age availability. Most tools using large language models, such as ChatGPT, Google Gemini or Microsoft Copilot, have their own minimum age limit for use. For example, ChatGPT can be used from the age of 13 with parental consent, but Google Gemini and Microsoft Copilot can be used from the age of 18 (Kroupa & Vykoukal, 2023). However, in practice, this can be circumvented – for example, ChatGPT or Microsoft Copilot can be used without logging in, which means that even younger children can access the tool, often without adult or teacher supervision. From a pedagogical point of view, it is crucial to keep in mind that despite the seemingly high competence of these models, these are systems that can create factual errors, so-called “hallucinations”. These errors can manifest themselves both in the substantive content and in linguistic analysis. For example, when practicing parts of speech in Czech, ChatGPT has a problem with recognizing non-part-of-speech transferred expressions – for example, the word “kolem” is not always correctly classified in the context of the sentence, just as words in indirect cases (“dědovi”) can be incorrectly classified. Similarly, when given the prompt: “Give me sentences with different pronouns and I will tell you which part they belong to,” the model often evaluates reflexive pronouns as a separate group, which does not correspond to the classification common in school practice.

Difficulties also arise when practicing adverbs and distinguishing them from particles. A task like: *„Come up with sentences with adverbs and I will look for them.“* can lead to confusion, because the AI itself sometimes incorrectly identifies the part of speech. Similarly, with prompts like: *„Give me a comparison and I will write adjectives with the same meaning.“*, the model is prone to errors in evaluating answers – it cannot properly work with context and differences in morphology. An important aspect is also the cultural and linguistic bias of the models, which were primarily trained on texts in English. Although the quality of outputs in Czech has improved significantly, language models still have difficulties with some specifics of Czech grammar, stylistics, or spelling. For example, in the task of listing the listed words after the ambivalent consonant B, ChatGPT writes these words: "to be, to live, bull, bright,

apartment, inhabitant, furniture, residential, former, to arrive, cattle", which is not a completely complete answer.

These limitations can be circumvented by creating your own model that is specifically trained for the given issue. However, this requires some financial resources, as this feature is not yet included in the free versions of the tools.

6 Conclusion

Although the introduction of generative artificial intelligence into education has been met with criticism – both from opponents of technological innovations and from those who point out legitimate risks – it cannot be overlooked that students and teachers are already actively using it. The key question therefore remains how educational researchers and didactics experts will respond to this transformation so that their work corresponds to current practice and the needs of schools.

A professional understanding of this issue can help teachers integrate AI in a meaningful way – in a way that supports student engagement and learning, not replaces it. Discussions about how to adapt educational practices in response to these technologies are already underway. Teachers are rethinking the form of assignments to make them meaningful even in an era when they can be easily generated by AI, and universities are beginning to question the relevance of traditional assessment methods such as final papers.

From a pedagogical perspective, it is essential to view the role of AI in the context of Bloom's Taxonomy. While generative models can effectively support lower cognitive levels such as memorization and comprehension, their greatest potential lies in freeing up space for higher-order thinking operations – analysis, synthesis, evaluation and creation. The challenge for teachers remains to design learning activities that lead to deeper processing of information, its critical evaluation and use in new contexts.

In this context, AI should never replace active student activity. The key is to formulate prompts that motivate students to think independently and develop their own skills. The goal of teaching should not be just to achieve superficial understanding, but to support higher levels of thinking, including creativity and critical evaluation of information.

At the same time, it is important to reflect on the limits of generative AI – not only technical and linguistic (e.g. hallucinations), but also didactic and ethical. Educators should guide students to understand the principles of AI functioning, point out its possible errors and support critical evaluation of its outputs. Only in this way will AI tools not become a mere trend, but a meaningful means of developing students' digital and cognitive competences.

Generative AI thus presents not only a challenge but also an opportunity – to redefine educational goals, innovate teaching methods and develop digital literacy. However, it is crucial that its integration is thoughtful and focused on developing critical thinking, creativity and a responsible approach to technology. The future of education in the AI era will depend on the ability of teachers and institutions to adapt to new conditions while actively co-creating

the direction in which education will take – with an emphasis on higher cognitive levels remaining essential for its meaningful inclusion.

Acknowledgements and affiliations

This work was supported by the project "Human-centered AI for a sustainable and adaptable society", reg. no.: CZ.02.01.01/00/23_025/0008691, co-funded by the European Union.

This text has not yet been published, it is an original text and is not currently being offered to other journals for publication.

7 Reference

- Anderson, L. W., & Krathwohl, D. R. (2001). *A Taxonomy for Learning, Teaching and Assessing A Revision of Bloom's Taxonomy of Educational Objectives Complete Edition*. Longman. <https://scirp.org/reference/referencespapers?referenceid=1223916>
- Bandi, A., Adapa, P. V. S. R., & Kuchi, Y. E. V. P. K. (2023). The Power of Generative AI: A Review of Requirements, Models, Input–Output Formats, Evaluation Metrics, and Challenges. In *Future Internet* (Vol. 15, Issue 8). <https://doi.org/10.3390/fi15080260>
- Bozkurt, A., Xiao, J., Farrow, R., Bai, J. Y. H., Nerantzi, C., Moore, S., Dron, J., Stracke, C. M., Singh, L., Crompton, H., Koutropoulos, A., Terentev, E., Pazurek, A., Nichols, M., Sidorkin, A. M., Costello, E., Watson, S., Mulligan, D., Honeychurch, S., ... Asino, T. I. (2024). The manifesto for teaching and learning in a time of Generative AI: A critical collective stance to better navigate the future. *Open Praxis*, 16(4), 487–513. <https://doi.org/10.55982/OPENPRAXIS.16.4.777>
- Chen, Y.-C., & Hou, H.-T. (2024). Design and Evaluation of the Framework of ChatGPT-Based Situational Non-Player Character Scaffolding for Educational Games. *2024 16th IIAI International Congress on Advanced Applied Informatics (IIAI-AAI)*, 720–721. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IIAI-AAI63651.2024.00152>
- D'hondt, S., Östman, J.-O., & Verschueren, J. (2009). *The Pragmatics of Interaction* (Vol. 4). John Benjamins Publishing Company. <https://doi.org/10.1075/hoph.4>
- European Commission. (2023). *What Is a Large Language Model?* <https://knowledge-centre-translation-interpretation.ec.europa.eu/en/news/what-large-language-model>
- Galindo-Domínguez, H., Delgado, N., de la Maza, M. S., & Expósito, E. (2024). An experimental analysis of the relationship between the evaluations of artificial intelligence and pre-service teachers. *EduTec, Revista Electrónica de Tecnología Educativa*, 89, 84–104. <https://doi.org/10.21556/edutec.2024.89.3509>
- Hartman, D. K. (2025). Improving the intellectual well-being of students using Generative AI tools to customize texts for learning. *Pedagogical Dialogue*, 4(50), 10–31. <https://doi.org/10.62670/2308-7668.2024.50.4.001>
- IBM. (n.d.). *What is generative AI?* Retrieved February 6, 2025, from <https://research.ibm.com/blog/what-is-generative-ai>

- IPSOS. (2025). *DĚTI A AI Report z dotazování mladých ve věku 12-17 let*. https://www.vodafone.cz/_sys_/FileStorage/download/4/3021/ipsos-a-vodafone-deti-a-ai-report.pdf
- Jauhiainen, J. S., & Guerra, A. G. (2023). Generative AI and ChatGPT in School Children's Education: Evidence from a School Lesson. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(18). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151814025>
- Kopecký Kamil. (2024). *S generativní umělou inteligencí ve škole opatrně, moc prosím (3 příklady použití GenAI)*. Kamil Kopecký (Blog). <https://kopeckykamil.cz/index.php/blog/405-s-generativni-umelou-inteligenci-ve-skole-opatrne-nekolik-prikladu>
- Kopecký Kamil, Voráč Dominik, & Szotkowski René. (2024). *Čeští žáci a umělá inteligence*.
- Korzynski, P., Mazurek, G., Krzypkowska, P., & Kurasinski, A. (2023). Artificial intelligence prompt engineering as a new digital competence: Analysis of generative AI technologies such as ChatGPT. *Entrepreneurial Business and Economics Review*, 11(3). <https://doi.org/10.15678/EBER.2023.110302>
- Kroupa, P., & Vykoukal, O. (2023). *Využití generativní AI ve školách - právní pohled*. <https://aidetem.cz/vyuziti-generativni-umele-inteligence-ve-skolach-pravni-pohled/>
- Microsoft. (2023). *What are large language models (LLMs)?* <https://azure.microsoft.com/en-us/resources/cloud-computing-dictionary/what-are-large-language-models-llms>
- Müllerová, O., Hoffmannová, J., & Schneiderová, E. (1992). *Mluvená čeština v autentických textech*. H&H.
- Oregon State University. (2024). *Advancing meaningful learning in the age of AI*. <https://ecampus.oregonstate.edu/faculty/artificial-intelligence-tools/blooms-taxonomy-revisited/>
- Peck, B. (2023). Data Scientist? AI Prompt Engineer? Or Both? *Medical Marketing and Media*, 58(7).
- Rámcový vzdělávací program pro základní vzdělávání*. (2021).
- Stanny, C. J. (2016). Reevaluating bloom's taxonomy: What measurable verbs can and cannot say about student learning. *Education Sciences*, 6(4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/EDUCSCI6040037>
- STEM. (2024). *Nástroje umělé inteligence již vyzkoušelo 45 % zkoumaných žáků a studentů, ukazuje výzkum "Jak se učíme my" pro Někračni. Jak Se Učíme My*. <https://www.stem.cz/nastroje-umele-inteligence-jiz-vyzkouselo-45-zkoumanych-zaku-a-studentu-ukazuje-vyzkum-jak-se-ucime-pro-nekrachni/>
- Villan, F., & P. dos Santos, R. (2023). ChatGPT as Co-Advisor in Scientific Initiation: Action Research with Project-Based Learning in Elementary Education. *Acta Scientiae*, 25(6), 60–117. <https://doi.org/10.17648/acta.scientiae.7474>
- Walter, Y. (2024). Embracing the future of Artificial Intelligence in the classroom: the relevance of AI literacy, prompt engineering, and critical thinking in modern education. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 21(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-024-00448-3>
- Willey, L., White, B. J., & Deale, C. S. (2023). Teaching AI in the college course: introducing the AI prompt development life cycle (PDLC). *Issues in Information Systems*, 24(2). https://doi.org/10.48009/2_iis_2023_111
- Wilson, L. O. (2016). *Anderson and Krathwohl Bloom's Taxonomy Revised Understanding the New Version of Bloom's Taxonomy*. https://quincycollege.edu/wp-content/uploads/Anderson-and-Krathwohl_Revised-Blooms-Taxonomy.pdf

